

NERCARSF Photography Data Base

Introduction

The aim of this document is to give a brief overview of the provisional Photography Database. A brief description is given for each table of the dbase, its relationship with the other tables and includes also of the field data types and sizes.

Aircraft

Details of the aircraft deployed

Relationships: YYYYPhotoArchive.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Aircraft_ID	Number	Long integer	PRIMARY KEY
Registration	Text	10	
Aircraft_Type	Text	30	

Camera_Details

Large Format Camera details

Relationships: YYYYPhotoArchive.mdb Calibration_Parameter.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Camera_ID	Number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Camera_Model_Type	Text	50	
Lenses_Model	Text	50	
Focal_Length	number	single	
Filter_Type	Text	50	

Calibration_Parameters

Details of the camera calibration parameters

Relationships: Camera_Details.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Camera_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Calibration Number	text	50	
Date	date/time		
Performed By	Text	50	
Lenses Model	Text	50	
Lenses Serial Numbe	Text	50	
Lenses Type	Text	50	
Calibrated Principal Distance (mm)	number	single	
Coordinate of Point of Symmetry x	number	single	
Coordinate of point of Symmetry y	number	single	
Coordinate of Principal Point of Autocollimation x	number	double	
Coordinate of Principal Point of Autocollimation y	number	double	
Radial Distortion1 at (mm)*	number	integer	

**Note Specify distances (6 different) along 4 semi-diagonal where the distortion are measured*

Semi Diagonal1 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal1 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal1 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal1 (4)	number	single
Mean1	number	single
Radial Distortion2 at (mm)	number	integer
Semi Diagonal2 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal2 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal2 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal2 (4)	number	single
Mean2	number	single
Radial Distortion3 at (mm)	number	integer
Semi Diagonal3 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal3 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal3 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal3 (4)	number	single
Mean3	number	single
Radial Distortion4 at (mm)	number	integer
Semi Diagonal4 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal4 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal4 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal4 (4)	number	single
Mean4	number	single
Radial Distortion5 at (mm)	number	integer
Semi Diagonal5 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal5 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal5 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal5 (4)	number	single
Mean5	number	single
Radial Distortion6 at (mm)	number	integer
Semi Diagonal6 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal6 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal6 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal6 (4)	number	single
Mean6	number	single
Radial Distortion7 at (mm)	number	integer
Semi Diagonal7 (1)	number	single
Semi Diagonal7 (2)	number	single
Semi Diagonal7 (3)	number	single
Semi Diagonal7 (4)	number	single
Mean7	number	single
Fiducal Coords FCx*	number	single

**Note Centre of Fiducial Marks (in x)*

Fiducial Coords Fcy*	number	single
<i>*Note Centre of Fiducial Marks (in y)</i>		
Coords Sx*	number	single
<i>*Note Point of Best Symmetry</i>		
Coords Sy	number	single
Coords PPAx*	number	single
<i>*Note Principal Point of Autocollimation</i>		
Coords PPAy	number	single
<i>*Note Principal Point of Autocollimation</i>		
Fiducial Coords Corner X1	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner Y1	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner X2	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner Y2	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner X3	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner Y3	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner X4	number	single
Fiducial Coords Corner Y4	number	single
Distances (Diag) 1-3	number	single
Distances (Diag) 2-4	number	single
Distances (Side) 3-4	number	single
Distances (Side) 2-3	number	single
Distances (Side) 4-1	number	single
Optimum Distance Diagonale	number	single
Max Error (diagonal)	number	single
Optimum Distance Side	number	single
Max Error (side)	number	single

Operator

Operator Details

Relationships:YYYYPhotoArchive.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Operator_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Operator_First_Name	Text	30	
Operator_Surname	Text	30	

Pilot

Pilot Details

Relationships:YYYYPhotoArchive.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Pilot_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Pilot_First_Name	Text	30	
Pilot_Surname	Text	30	

Roll_Info

Details of the rolls archived

Relationships:YYYYPhotoArchive.mdb Film_Types.mdb Film_processing.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Roll_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Film_Type_ID	number	integer	
NERC_Roll_Number	text	10	
Usage	text	10	
Processing_Date	date		
Titled*	y/n		

**Note A flag field, film titled when flagged (y)*

Film_Types

Film general information

Relationships: Roll_Info.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Film_Type_ID	Number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Producer	Text	20	
Type	Text	50	
Sensitivity	Text	20	
Dimensions_width (cm)	number	integer	
Dimensions_length (m)	number	integer	

Film_Processing

Details of the rolls processing and printing history

Relationship: Rolls_Info.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Roll_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Printing_Company	Text	50	
Processing_Company	Text	50	

Project_Details

Project NERC code, site name, contact, central location (lat/long and Nat. Grid), datum and photographic details of project.

Relationship :YYYYPhotoArchive.mdb, Datum.mdb

Fields details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Project_ID	number	double	PRIMARY KEY
Site_Name	Text	50	
PI_First_Name	Text	30	
PI_Surname	Text	30	
Centre_Site_Latitude*	number	double	
<i>*In Decimal Degrees</i>			
Centre_Site_Longitude*	number	double	
<i>*In Decimal Degrees (negative indicate Longitude West)</i>			
Centre_Site_Easting_Nat_Grid	number	single	
Centre_Site_Northing_Nat_Grid	number	single	
Datum_ID	number	integer	
Mono/Stereo	Text	10	
Photographic_Endlap_%	number	integer	
Photographic_Sidelap_%	number	integer	
Nominal_Scale_1:	number	integer	
Number_of_Runs	number	integer	
Total_Photo	number	integer	
Remarks	Text	50	

Datum

Datum details, used for specifying the Site parameter. Note that the lat/long positions of the frames in YYYYPhotoArchive is given in WGS84, different from the ones used in specifying the Project Details site parameters (e.g. Airy, OSGB 1936).

Relationships:Project_Details.mdb

Fields Details	Data Type	Size	Indexing
Datum_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Ellipsoid	Text	50	
Map Projection	Text	50	
National_Grid_Name	Text	50	

YYYYPhotoArchive

Core database, with frames information, acceptance details, date of acquisition etc. YYYY is the year of the archive, starting with 2000.

Relationships Roll_Info.mdb, Project_details.mdb, Aircraft.mdb, Operator.mdb, Pilot.mdb, Camera_Details.mdb, Photo_Status.mdb

Fields Description

Record_NR	Autonumber	long integer	PRIMARY KEY
Project_ID	number	double	

Roll_ID	number	integer	
Run_ID	number	integer	
<i>(Temporary modified as Text 50 to append data from Tracker dbase)</i>			
Frame_NR	number	integer	
Status_ID	number	integer	<u>Acceptance flags</u>
Photo_grid_northing*	number s	ingle	
<u>*Location of the frame centre in National Grid Northing Coordinates (metres)</u>			
Photo_grid_easting*	number	single	
<u>*Location of the frame centre in National Grid Easting Coordinates (metres)</u>			
Altitude_GPS*	number	long integer	
<u>Altitude above WGS84 spheroid</u>			
WGS_potoposition_long*	number	double	
<u>*Longitude in WGS84 Spheroid, in decimal degrees</u>			
WGS_fotoposition_lat*	number	double	
<u>*Latitude in WGS84 Spheroid, in decimal degrees</u>			
Acquisition_date*		date	
<u>*Temporary modified as Text 50 to append data from Tacker dbase</u>			
Camera_ID	number	integer	
Aircraft_ID	number	integer	
Pilot_ID	number	integer	
Operator_ID	number	integer	

Photo_Status

Descriptor of the acceptance status for the frames. It could assume 3 values:

- 0 Off-track frame
- 1 Rejected Cloud/shadow/haze covering > 15% of the frame area
- 2 Accepted

Field details

Status_ID	number	integer	PRIMARY KEY
Description	Text	20	